

FIRST RECORD OF THE DRAGONFLY BITING MIDGE *FORCIPOMYIA PALUDIS* (DIPTERA: CERATOPOGONIDAE) IN UKRAINE

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Lemke, M. & Hryniuk, P. First record of the dragonfly biting midge *Forcipomyia paludis* (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae) in Ukraine. — Based on unnoticed photograph of immature adult male Downy Emerald *Cordulia aenea* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Odonata: Libellulidae) with three females of the dragonfly biting midge *Forcipomyia (Pterobosca) paludis* (Macfie, 1936) parasitizing on it in the National Nature Park “Northern Podillya”, Lviv Region, western Ukraine, the latter species is recorded from Ukraine for the first time. The photo was uploaded in the open natural history online database of the Ukrainian Biodiversity Information Network (UkrBIN) and was later discovered there. This record extends the known range of *F. paludis* to Eastern Europe.

Key words: Odonata, dragonfly, *Cladium mariscus*, Anisoptera, Ukraine, Eastern Europe, first record.

Лемке, М. і Гринюк, П. Перша знахідка *Forcipomyia paludis* (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae) в Україні. — Три особини мокреця бабкового *Forcipomyia (Pterobosca) paludis* (Macfie, 1936) були сфотографовані непоміченими у національному природному парку «Північне Поділля» Львівської області (західна Україна) під час смоктання гемолімфи на молодому самці кордулії бронзової *Cordulia aenea* (Odonata: Libellulidae). Фотографію було завантажено на відкриту природничу базу даних Української мережі інформації з біорізноманіття (УкрБІН) та знайдено там пізніше. Це перша знахідка виду в Україні, яка розширює відомий ареал *F. paludis* до Східної Європи.

Ключові слова: Odonata, різнокрилі бабки, Anisoptera, Україна, Східна Європа, перша знахідка, *Cladium mariscus*.

Introduction

Within the family Ceratopogonidae, the dragonfly biting midge *Forcipomyia (Pterobosca) paludis* (Macfie, 1936) is the only European species exclusively parasitizing on dragonflies (Wildermuth & Martens, 2019): the females suck haemolymph mainly from the veins of the wings (Wildermuth & Martens, 2007). Martens *et al.* (2008) showed that searching in photos of dragonflies is a very simple but very effective way of detecting these insects, which are only about 2 mm small. Recently, citizen scientists have been uploading many photos of dragonflies in open natural history online databases. Analysis of these photos revealed many (first) records of *F. paludis* for many European countries (*e. g.*, Cordero-Rivera *et al.*, 2019; Vinko *et al.*, 2017; each with further references). So, *F. paludis* has been recorded in all greater countries in western, southern and central Europe (exception: Latvia), as well as in northern (Sweden: Vinko *et al.*, 2017;

Denmark: Wasscher *et al.*, 2021a) and southeastern Europe (Bosnia and Herzegovina: Vinko *et al.*, 2017).

Outside of Europe, evidences were made in Asia (Turkey: Wasscher *et al.*, 2021a, Georgia: Wildermuth *et al.*, 2019) and in Africa (Morocco: Boudot *et al.*, 2019; “Uganda” in Remm (1988) seems doubtful).

The Downy Emerald *Cordulia aenea* (Linnaeus, 1758) has a Euro-Siberian distribution (Boudot *et al.*, 2017) in a broad range from western Europe to Kamchatka, northeastern China and Japan and from the southern Balkans to lowland Fennoscandia (Kalkman & Lohr, 2015). It occurs almost throughout Ukraine, is very common in the north and rarer in the south (Gorb *et al.*, 2000). Matushkina (2020) lists it as a common species for central Ukraine. In the “IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2020” it is listed as “Least Concern” (“LC”; Clausnitzer, 2020). *Cordulia aenea* is not included in the Red Data Book of Ukraine (Akimov, 2009).

Study site and method

On 9.06.2021 PH visited the central part of the National Nature Park (NNP) “Northern Podillya” (Національний природний парк «Північне Поділля»), c. 2.5 km southwest of Pidhirtsi, Zolochiv District, Lviv Region (WGS84: 49.9319° N, 24.9487° E, c. 400 m a. s. l.). At 12:06 h EEST (UTC+03:00) he photographed a male of the unknown to him *Cordulia aenea*, resting on the outer leaves of a hornbeam tree (Fig. 1). The surrounding area was dominated by small-scale agriculture (fields, meadows) and forestry (hornbeam-beech forest). Water bodies were completely absent. Larger water and bog areas are at least 4.5 km away from the site; the nearest is the Olesko bog area to the north, covering an area of approx. 400 hectares (Geoportal, 2022). PH uploaded his records in the open natural history online database of the Ukrainian

Biodiversity Information Network (UkrBIN, 2022). Here the dragonfly was later determined as a male *C. aenea*.

Stimulated by the recent publications (see above), ML examined all of the 2,200+ photos of Ukrainian dragonflies stored in the online database of the Ukrainian Biodiversity Information Network on 15.01.2022. Ultimately, only the male *C. aenea* photographed by PH on 9.06.2021 showed an infestation of *F. paludis*.

Discussion

The discovery of *F. paludis* in western Ukraine increases the number of European countries with occurrences of the dragonfly biting midge to 23. The finding extends its range to Eastern Europe. The site within the NNP “Northern Podillya” is just 130 km east of the only record of *F. paludis* in Poland (Dominiak &

Fig. 1. Three female dragonfly biting midges *Forcipomyia paludis* on the hindwings of a male *Cordulia aenea* (inlay -- same, enlarged; arrows indicate midges). National Nature Park “Pivnichne Podillia”, Lviv Region, Ukraine (9.06.2021).

Photo: Petro Hryniuk.

Michalczyk, 2009). Both sites are in the direct catchment area of the river Bug.

This first record in the Ukraine continues a series of first and new records of *F. paludis*, which were brought about by intensive research in the stocks of dragonfly photos posted in open natural history online databases. Without photos from these databases, which are mostly uploaded by citizen scientists, knowledge about the occurrence of many taxa would be far less extensive. These databases are particularly valuable for inconspicuous and not commonly known taxa such as *F. paludis*.

The glossy wings and the fresh, shiny body color indicate that PH photographed an immature male *C. aenea*. Because there are no water bodies in the surroundings of this site, the immature male had to fly a distance of at least 4.5 km; nearest larger water bodies: Olesko bog area (Geoportal, 2022).

It is remarkable that *F. paludis* was also observed so far from the nearest water body. This manifests the strong anchoring of *F. paludis* in the wing veins by its proboscis. The anchorage had to withstand the centrifugal forces generated by wing flapping and the wind forces generated by the flight of the host. The fact that the parasites were able to withstand the forces acting on them for so long is also due to the chosen anchorage place. Anchorage near the wing base reduces centrifugal forces during wing flapping, and the wide thoracic plate prevents stronger wind forces. The place on an inward vein (angle between adjacent wing cells less than 180°) also reduces wind forces.

This record of *F. paludis* described here also seems to confirm Wasscher *et al.* (2021a, b), who noticed a co-occurrence of the dragonfly biting midge and the Great fensedge *Cladium mariscus* (L.) (Pohl) in Europe. Although dragonflies infested with *F. paludis* have also been recorded at other localities, they found that most records are in localities with *C. mariscus* or in the immediate vicinity. Here the level of infestation was considerably higher (Wasscher *et al.*, 2021a, b).

Cladium mariscus also occurs in Ukraine. Here it is rare and classified as “Vulnerable” (“вразливий”) in the Red Data Book of Ukraine (Andrienko *et al.*, 2009). Out of 20 known sites, 16 are in western regions (Andrienko *et al.*, 2009) with a clear center in the northeastern Lviv Region. The locality of the male *C. aenea* infested with *F. paludis* presented here is almost surrounded by known localities of *C. mariscus*: 20 km to the north, 12 km to the southeast, 18 km to the south and 16 km to the southwest (Borsukevych, 2008; Batochenko, 2019; Ralo & Yurechko, 2019; Yurechko, 2019; UkrBIN, 2022).

In Ukrainian, in addition to the Latin name, species are very often also named with Ukrainian vernacular names. We propose this new name to be “мокрець бабковий”, according to the biology of *F. paludis*, being specialized parasite of Odonata.

An intensive search in areas with known occurrences of this plant in Ukraine could yield further records of *F. paludis* for this country. It should be carried out in the

area of NNP “Northern Podillya” and its surroundings, the place of our first record. Another promising area seems to be the Danube Delta and its surroundings. From the Danube Delta, Damian-Georgescu (1973) reports the first and so far only record of *F. paludis* for Romania: “Distribution: Africa, USSR. In our country it was captured in the Danube Delta (Puiuieț).” (“Răspîndire: Africa, U. R. S. S. În țară a fost capturată în Delta Dunării (Puiuieț).”) The site “Puiuieț” refers to a lake (and a short canal) within the Danube Delta, c. 3.5 km east of Caraorman (Tulcea county; WGS84: 45.0829° N, 29.4340° E). Interestingly, only c. 45 km to the northeast is a known occurrence of *Cladium mariscus* at Vylkove, Izmail District, Odessa Region (Andrienko *et al.*, 2009).

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